

Thermophysical properties of mixtures of 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methylsulfate or 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium thiocyanate with alcohols

Estela Lladosa*, Sonia Loras, Helena Poy and Lohengrin Caballero.

Departamento de Ingeniería Química, Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingeniería, Universitat de València, 46100 Burjassot, Valencia, Spain

Abstract

In the present paper, densities, speeds of sound and viscosities of four binary mixtures containing the ionic liquids 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methylsulfate and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium thiocyanate mixed with ethanol or 1-propanol were measured at 101.3 kPa in the range of (283.15-323.15) K, along the whole composition range. From these experimental data, the excess molar volume and the excess isentropic compressibility of pure components and mixtures were calculated and satisfactorily fitted using the Redlich-Kister polynomial equation. It can be confirmed that the organic compounds have a strong effect on the thermophysical properties of the studied ionic liquids. An increase in the alkyl chain length of 1-alcohol resulted in an increase in the excess deviation of excess molar volume.

Keywords: density; speed of sound; viscosity; [emim][Me₂SO₄]; [emim][SCN]; alcohols

1. Introduction

Due the unlimited number of potential combinations of cations and anions,¹ ionic liquids (ILs) have attracted the attention of numerous researches. This feature makes it possible to design the ILs to specific applications. ILs are currently being explored as solvents in biorefining processes² because of their attractive properties such as negligible vapour pressure and high thermal and chemical stability. In this context, the use of ILs as solvents for pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass has gained great attention since they can simultaneously dissolve carbohydrates and lignin³. Moreover, ILs are capable of dissolving a wide array of biomass types including softwood, hardwood and agricultural residues, in contrast with other pretreatment methods.⁴

To bring this approach to industrial applications, a low cost and simple method for IL recovery should be obtained. From preliminary studies^{5, 6} it was found that different types of organic solvents provided different solubility characteristics when the solvents were dissolved in a lignin-IL solution. IL and lignin recoveries by an organic solvent could be crucial solution for applying ILs for biomass pretreatment into an industrial scale. To that effect, ethanol and 1-propanol are organic solvents characteristic of full dissolution with IL with lignin precipitation⁵.

Due to their novelty in applying ILs for biomass pretreatment and to the wide variety of possible ILs, most of the ILs or (IL + organic solvent) mixtures still have their thermophysical properties poorly characterized, and a complete database is far from being achieved, despite the large number of papers published over the last decade⁷⁻¹⁰. Furthermore, the density and viscosity of multicomponent solutions play a significant role in industrial areas when it comes mass and heat transfer, as well as fluid flow. These thermophysical properties are essential for developing models for engineering applications or simulation processes and also fundamental for more in depth studying other thermodynamic and transport properties of solutions. Moreover, speeds of sound data are particularly useful in modelling the thermodynamic properties of real fluids.

ILs based on the 1-alkyl-3-methylimidazolium cation, $[C_n\text{mim}]$, are the most used and commonly studied ILs on the pretreatment of lignocellulosic biomass. There are publications concerning the suitability of ILs as solvents in biorefining processes.^{4, 11, 12}

According to these publications, the nature of the anions influenced the solubility of lignin in ILs. ILs containing large, non-coordinating anions as tetrafluoroborate and hexafluorophosphate were unsuitable as a solvent for lignin and IL with methylsulfate and trifluoromethanesulfonate anions appear to be effective solvents for lignin.

Due to the IL anion plays a crucial paper toward the pretreatment and processing of biomass, we studied in this paper the ILs share the cation 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium while being combined with two different anions. Particularly, in the current work, we are exploring the properties of mixtures of selected ILs such as 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methylsulfate ($[\text{emim}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4]$) and 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium thiocyanate ($[\text{emim}][\text{SCN}]$) with two organic solvents, ethanol and 1-propanol, over the whole range of compositions at $T = (283.15 \text{ to } 323.15) \text{ K}$ and at $p = 101 \text{ kPa}$. In addition, this paper is a continuation of our comprehensive investigation on the mixtures imidazolium-based ILs^{13, 14} + alcohols.

Despite the importance of imidazolium-based ILs in industrial applications, works dealing with the thermophysical properties of mixtures of $[\text{emim}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4]$ or $[\text{emim}][\text{SCN}]$ with solvents are scarce in the literature. In the published papers, data reported in literature are density¹⁵⁻²⁶ and viscosity^{17, 20, 22, 23, 27-28} of the pure $[\text{emim}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4]$ and density^{16, 29-38} and viscosity^{29-30, 34, 37, 38} of pure $[\text{emim}][\text{SCN}]$. Nevertheless, there are few references that report physical properties data of these ILs with ethanol or 1-propanol. As far as we know, data reported are densities of $[\text{emim}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4]$ + ethanol^{22, 39} and $[\text{emim}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4]$ + 1-propanol^{22, 40-41}, speed of sound of $[\text{emim}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4]$ + 1-propanol^{22, 26, 42} and viscosity of $[\text{emim}][\text{Me}_2\text{SO}_4]$ + 1-propanol.⁴² And only recent molecular simulation of $[\text{emim}][\text{SCN}]$ + ethanol⁴³ binary system have been reported in the literature.

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemicals

Ethanol (99.9% mass, for analysis ACS) and 1-propanol (>99.5% mass) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich. All solvents were degassed ultrasonically and held over molecular sieves (Aldrich, type 0.3 nm, 1.6 mm pellets). The ILs, [emim][Me₂SO₄] and [emim][SCN], were supplied by IoLiTec and desiccated at 0.2 kPa before its use. The chemical specifications of all materials are reported in Table 1.

2.2. Apparatus and procedure

Mixtures samples were prepared by weighing, using a Mettler Toledo AG245 scale analytical balance, with a resolution of $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ g. The uncertainty in mole fraction was estimated to be $2 \cdot 10^{-4}$.

In order to avoid water adsorption or to avoid evaporation of the alcohols, all samples were prepared just minutes before measurements. Moreover, repetition measurements with fresh samples from the same prepared mixtures were performed to confirm the reported uncertainties.

2.2.1. Densities and speed of sound

A digital vibrating-tube densimeter and speed of sound analyser (Anton Paar DSA 5000M) was used to measure the density ρ and the speed of sound u of binary mixtures and pure components. The apparatus was calibrated according to the manual instructions: with dry air and with Millipore quality water. Remarkable characteristics of the densimeter are its capacity to correct the influence of viscosity on the measurement, its proportional temperature controller that maintains the samples at a constant temperature and its bubble detection system. The accuracy of the temperature controller is 0.001 K. Taking into account the purity of chemical, standard uncertainties of measurements were estimated to be 0.01 K for temperature, $1.0 \text{ kg} \cdot \text{m}^{-3}$ for density and $0.2 \text{ m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$ for speed of sound.

2.2.2. Dynamic viscosities

Dynamic viscosities, η , were obtained using an Anton Paar AMVn falling ball automated viscometer. The temperature is controlled by a built-in Peltier thermostat with an accuracy of 0.01 K. Various calibrated capillary/ball combinations with different diameters (1.6 mm, 1.8 mm, and 3.0 mm) were selected to measurement of viscosities from (0.7 to 141) mPa·s. Taking into account the purity of chemicals, the standard uncertainty is associated with capillary size and this value was 0.034 mPa·s, 0.214 mPa·s and 0.958 mPa·s for capillaries with 1.6, 1.8, and 3.0 mm diameter, respectively.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Volumetric properties of pure ionic liquids

Experimental data of density, ρ , speed of sound, u , and dynamic viscosity, η , were obtained at atmospheric pressure from $T = (283.15-323.15)$ K for [emim][Me₂SO₄] and [emim][SCN]. In Table S1 of Appendix A (Supporting Information) the experimental data are shown. These data have been compared with data reported in literature and then deviations of our data from the literature were obtained. In Table S2 of Appendix A (Supporting Information), the literature data points, the average absolute relative deviation (δ_{ave}) and the maximum absolute relative deviation (δ_{max}) of our data from the literature have been reported.

3.2. Volumetric properties of liquid mixtures

In this paper, binary mixtures of [emim][Me₂SO₄] and [emim][SCN] + ethanol or + 1-propanol were prepared along the whole composition range. For each prepared mixture, density ρ , speed of sound, u , and dynamic viscosity, η , were measured.

From density and speed of sound experimental values, the molar volume, V_m , and the isentropic compressibility, κ_s , can be determined using Eqs. (1) and (2) respectively;

$$V_m = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^2 x_i M_i}{\rho} \quad (1)$$

$$\kappa_S = \frac{1}{\rho \cdot u^2} = \frac{V_m}{M_m \cdot u^2} \quad (2)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction of component i , M_i is the molar mass of pure component i and M_m is the molar mass of the mixture, defined as $M_m = \sum x_i M_i$

The combined standard uncertainty for molar volume and isentropic compressibility were estimated to be less than $1 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and 0.05 TPa^{-1} , respectively.

In Tables S3-S6 of Appendix B (Supporting Information) we have reported the experimental data of density ρ , speed of sound, u , and dynamic viscosity, η and the calculated values for the molar volume V_m , and the isentropic compressibility, κ_S for [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanol, [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol, [emim][SCN] + ethanol and [emim][SCN] + 1-propanol at $T = (283.15-323.15) \text{ K}$ and $p = 101 \text{ kPa}$.

The density, speed of sound and viscosity have been plotted as a function of the IL molar fraction at different temperatures in Figures 1-3. In addition, Figure 1a) include [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanol data from Requejo *et al.*²² and Wang *et al.*³⁹ and in Figure 1b) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol data from Requejo *et al.*²² and Dai *et al.*⁴⁰ are plotted. According to these figures, density data from this work are in good agreement with those reported in the literature.

A comparison of the experimental data of the binary system [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol with those previously reported by other authors^{26, 41, 42} was carried out as a Supporting Information. From Figure S1, it is possible to observe that our experimental density data are in agreement with data obtained by Sandhya *et al.*²⁶ being the maximum deviation of 0.62%. Regarding the density data reported by Alhaldi *et al.*⁴¹ a high deviation is observed (1.15%). These deviations can be attributed to impurities in the [emim][Me₂SO₄] such as water content where in data reported by Alhaldi *et al.*⁴¹ are higher which decrease density values. Moreover, a comparison of viscosity data was also included in Figure S1. As it can be seen, the viscosity data reported by AlTuwaim *et al.*⁴² present large differences with our experimental data, mainly at the lowest temperature. The deviations in these

values are probably due to impurities of the ionic liquids and the applied methodology used to measure the viscosity. In the previous reported data⁴² a rotational viscometer was used instead of a falling ball viscometer.

The density, speed of sound and viscosity decrease when the temperature increases, for all the pure components and their mixtures. Therefore, the molar volume and the isentropic compressibility of the same components increase with the temperature.

The effect of anion ([Me₂SO₄] or [SCN]) on density, speed of sound and viscosity of the mixture lead the large value of all in the case of [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-alcohols as compared to [emim][SCN] + 1-alcohols systems. Most authors⁴⁴⁻⁴⁶ state that the density and viscosity of IL increases with the molecular weight of the anion. Clearly our results follow the mentioned rule: [Me₂SO₄] (111.1 g·mol⁻¹) > [SCN] (58.08 g·mol⁻¹).

3.3. Excess properties of liquid mixtures

It is possible to calculate the difference between these values and ideal values, because it is known the values of volumetric properties. These deviations are called excess properties, Q^E , and are defined as the difference between the actual value of the property in the mixture, Q , and that corresponding for an ideal mixture at the same thermodynamic condition, Q^{id} :

$$Q^E = Q - Q^{id} \quad (3)$$

If it is considered that the ideal molar volume is equal to the sum of the products obtained after multiply the mole fraction and the molar volume of each mixture component, the excess molar volume is obtained as follows.

$$V_m^E = V_m - \sum_{i=1}^2 x_i \cdot V_i^0 \quad (4)$$

where x_i is the mole fraction of component i and V_i^0 is the molar volume of pure component i at the mixture temperature and pressure.

In the same way, the excess isentropic compressibility κ_S^E of a mixture is defined as

$$\kappa_S^E = \kappa_S - \kappa_S^{id} \quad (5)$$

where κ_S^{id} is the isentropic compressibility for the ideal mixture at the same thermodynamic state and can be calculated using the following expression (Dohuret *et al.*⁴⁷)

$$\kappa_S^{id} = \sum_{i=1}^2 \phi_i \cdot \kappa_{S,i}^0 - T \left[\sum_{i=1}^2 \left(\frac{\phi_i \cdot V_i^0 \cdot (\alpha_{p,i}^0)^2}{C_{p,i}^0} \right) - \frac{V_m^{id} \cdot (\alpha_{p,m}^{id})^2}{C_{p,m}^{id}} \right] \quad (6)$$

where $\phi_i (= x_i \cdot V_i^0 / V_m^{id})$ is the volume fraction of component i , while κ_S^{id} , $\alpha_{p,i}^0$ and $C_{p,i}^0$ are the isentropic compressibility, the isobaric coefficient of thermal expansion and the isobaric molar heat capacity of pure component i at the mixture temperature and pressure, respectively. On the other hand, $\alpha_{p,m}^{id}$ and $C_{p,m}^{id}$ are the isobaric coefficient of thermal expansion and the molar heat capacity, respectively, of the ideal mixture defined as:

$$\alpha_{p,m}^{id} = \phi_1 \cdot \alpha_{p,1}^0 + \phi_2 \cdot \alpha_{p,2}^0 \quad (7)$$

$$C_{p,m}^{id} = x_1 \cdot C_{p,1}^0 + x_2 \cdot C_{p,2}^0 \quad (8)$$

Furthermore, the isobaric thermal expansivities $\alpha_{p,i}^0$ of pure components were obtained from polynomial fit of our density data using the expression

$$\alpha_p = \frac{1}{V_m} \left(\frac{\partial V_m}{\partial T} \right)_p = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \right)_p \quad (9)$$

All ideal properties have the same standard uncertainties that the real properties.

Isobaric molar heat capacities, $C_{p,i}^0$ values for [emim][Me₂SO₄] and [emim][SCN] were obtained from Ficke *et al.*¹⁶ and for ethanol and 1-propanol were obtained from a correlation proposed in the Daubert and Danner data compilation⁴⁶.

Excess properties, $Q^E (= V_m^E \text{ or } \kappa_S^E)$ can be expressed as a function of mixture compositions using the Redlich-Kister equation:⁵⁰

$$Q^E = x_i x_j \sum_{p=0}^m A_p (x_i - x_j)^p$$

(10)

where A_p is the polynomial coefficient, and m is the degree of the polynomial expansion. Though temperature does not explicitly appear in equation (10), it is implicit in the coefficients, since they are a second degree function of temperature:

$$A_p = A_{p_a} \cdot T^2 + A_{p_b} \cdot T + A_{p_c} \quad (11)$$

where A_{p_a} , A_{p_b} and A_{p_c} are the fitting parameters. These fitting parameters were obtained by correlating experimental data. This correlation was performed minimizing an objective function defined as the sum of absolute standard deviations, σ , which were calculated using the following expression:

$$\sigma = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_i^{n_{dat}} (Q_{exp.}^E - Q_{calc.}^E)^2}{n_{dat}}} \quad (12)$$

in which n_{dat} is the number of experimental data point. Results of these correlations are given in Tables 2 and 3. As it can see, equation (10) predicts accurately all excess properties.

Figures 4-5 show, respectively, experimental values of V_m^E and κ_S^E against the IL mole fraction for the IL + alcohol binary mixtures studied at working temperatures, in addition to the curves obtained using the adjustment parameters of Table 2 and 3. For excess molar volume and excess isentropic compressibility properties, all of the curves are asymmetrical, which are rather common in mixtures containing two components with a large molar volume difference, although the effect being more pronounced for the excess isentropic compressibility. The relationship between V_m^E and x_I depends largely on the IL and its amount in the mixture. For all mixtures, two zones can be established. For the excess molar volume, curves present a minimum at $x_I \cong 0.3-0.4$, while for excess isentropic compressibility this minimum is given at $x_I \cong 0.2-0.3$.

The V_m^E values for the mixtures became more negative with the increase in temperatures from (283.15 to 323.15) K. The negative V_m^E values suggest the presence of strong specific interaction between 1-alkanols and ILs. The negative V_m^E behaviour can be referred to cross hydrogen bonding between the most acidic hydrogen of an imidazolium-IL cation and hydroxyl group (-OH) of 1-alkanols and also owing to the interactions of ion-dipole between 1-alkanols and IL. This behaviour is particular for this kind of mixtures, as also previously reported by Iglesias *et al.*⁵⁰ and similar pattern was also reported for binary mixtures of [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanoic acid and propanoic acid²⁵. Furthermore, the relative small size of 1-alkanols fit well into the free volumes between the relative large ions of the IL, resulting in more efficient packing in the mixture than in pure components and thus resulting in the negative excess volume molar values, which it does not happen with mixtures with longer chain 1-alkanols. This behaviour was also reported by other authors^{22, 50} and it can be seen in Figure 6, where it has been compared the excess volume data for [emim][Me₂SO₄] for mixtures with different 1-alcohols from literature^{26, 51} at constant temperature. An increase of alcohol chain length leads to less negative values of this excess property, the molecular interaction of [C_nmim]-based ILs with 1-alcohols fall the following order: ethanol > 1-propanol > 1-butanol > 1-pentanol > 1-hexanol > 1-heptanol > 1-octanol > 1-nonanol.

In Figure 7 it can be seen the effect of different anions from the literature for other [emim]-based ILs with ethanol and 1-propanol. As expected, the densities, and therefore the V_m^E , are related to the molar masses of the ions. Therefore, as it can be seen in this figure, and previously reported by Jacquemin *et al.*,⁵⁶ ILs containing the anion [NTf₂], having the higher molar masses of the studied anions (287.78 g·mol⁻¹), exhibit the highest density followed by ILs containing [triflate] (149.07 g·mol⁻¹) < [EtSO₄] (126.13 g·mol⁻¹) < [Me₂SO₄] (111.1 g·mol⁻¹) < [HSO₄] (97.07 g·mol⁻¹) < [SCN] (58.08 g·mol⁻¹). Moreover, V_m^E values for the binary of [emim][Me₂SO₄] + alkanol (ethanol or 1-propanol) are more negative compare to the mixture of [emim][EtSO₄] + alkanol published^{52, 54}, indicating the enhancement specific or unlike interactions in the mixtures with the addition of a -CH₂- group in the

anion in the IL molecule. This phenomenon is consistent with the results published by Domńska and co-workers.⁵⁴

4. Conclusions

Experimental values of density ρ , viscosity η and speed of sound u have been obtained at different temperatures (283.15, 293.15, 303.15, 313.15 and 323.15 K) for mixtures formed by an IL ([emim][Me₂SO₄] or [emim][SCN]) and ethanol or + 1-propanol. All measurements were performed at atmospheric pressure.

The molar volume, V and the isentropic compressibility, κ_s have been calculated from experimental data. Moreover, the ideal values of these properties have also been determined using theoretical equations. In addition, the excess molar volume V_m^E and the excess isentropic compressibility κ_s^E have been obtained. The relationship between excess properties and IL mole fraction has been expressed as a Redlich-Kister equation for each property and the thermodynamic excess properties of liquid mixtures were discussed in terms of strong intermolecular interactions.

The excess molar volume V_m^E and the excess isentropic compressibility κ_s^E are always negative in the whole range of compositions and temperatures, and they decrease, that is, they become more negative, with increasing temperature.

Examining our results, it can be seen that the thermophysical properties of ILs depends on the nature of the involved organic solvent and the nature of anion and cation of the ILs. On the one hand, we have studied the influence of alkyl chain length of 1-alcohols on the molecular interaction of [emim][Me₂SO₄] IL. An increase in the alkyl chain length of the 1-alcohol resulted in an increase in the deviation of V_m^E . On the other hand, the excess molar volume is affected by the anion of the IL and is related to the molar masses of the ions, ILs containing higher molar masses exhibit higher density.

Supporting Information Available

Pure IL properties (Table S1), comparison of IL properties with literature data (Table S2), density, speed of sound, dynamic viscosity, molar volume, excess molar volume, isentropic compressibility and excess isentropic compressibility for binary mixtures of ILs + ethanol or 1-propanol (Tables S3-S6), comparison of the experimental data of the binary system [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol with those previously reported by other authors (Figure S1).

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(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 1. Density ρ for the IL (1) + ethanol or 1-propanol (2) binary systems at different temperatures; \circ , 283.15 K; \circ , 293.15 K; \triangle , 303.15 K; \blacksquare , 313.15 K and \square , 323.15 K. (a) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanol, \times , 288.15 K; \otimes , 298.15 K; \star , 308.15 K data from Requejo et al.²², ∇ , 293.15 K data from Wang et al.³⁹ (b) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol, \times , 288.15 K; \otimes , 298.15 K \star , 308.15 K data from Requejo et al.²², ∇ , 293.15 K; \diamond , 313.15 K data from Dai et al.⁴⁰ (c) [emim][SCN] + ethanol (d) [emim][SCN] + 1-propanol.

Figure 2. Speed of sound u for the IL (1) + ethanol or 1-propanol (2) binary systems at different temperatures; \circ , 283.15 K; \bullet , 293.15 K; \triangle , 303.15 K; \blacksquare , 313.15 K and \square , 323.15 K. (a) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanol (b) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol (c) [emim][SCN] + ethanol (d) [emim][SCN] + 1-propanol.

Figure 3. Viscosity η for the IL (1) + ethanol or 1-propanol (2) binary systems at different temperatures; \circ , 283.15 K; \bullet , 293.15 K; \triangle , 303.15 K; \blacksquare , 313.15 K and \square , 323.15 K. (a) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanol (b) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol (c) [emim][SCN] + ethanol (d) [emim][SCN] + 1-propanol.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 4. Excess molar volume V_m^E for the IL (1) + ethanol or 1-propanol (2) binary systems at different temperatures; \circ , 283.15 K; \bullet , 293.15 K; \triangle , 303.15 K; \blacksquare , 313.15 K and \square , 323.15 K. (a) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanol (b) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol (c) [emim][SCN] + ethanol (d) [emim][SCN] + 1-propanol.

(a)

(b)

(c)

(d)

Figure 5. Excess isentropic compressibility κ_S^E for the IL (1) + ethanol or 1-propanol (2) binary systems at different temperatures; \circ , 283.15 K; \bullet , 293.15 K; \triangle , 303.15 K; \blacksquare , 313.15 K and \square , 323.15 K. (a) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + ethanol (b) [emim][Me₂SO₄] + 1-propanol (c) [emim][SCN] + ethanol (d) [emim][SCN] + 1-propanol.

Figure 6. Excess molar volume V_m^E for the IL (1) + alcohol (2). [emim][Me₂SO₄] with ●, ethanol; ○, 1-propanol; △, 1-butanol²⁶; ■, 1-pentanol²⁶; □, 1-hexanol²⁶; ◆, 1-heptanol⁵¹; ◇, 1-octanol⁵¹; ×, 1-nonanol⁵¹ at 303.15 K.

Figure 7. Excess molar volume V_m^E for the [emim]-based IL (1) + alcohol (2). (a) [emim][anion] + ethanol: ●, [Me₂SO₄] at 293.15 K; △, [SCN] at 293.15 K; ○, [EtSO₄]⁵⁰ at 298.15 K; ■, [NTf₂]¹³ at 298.15 K; ×, [triflate]⁹ at 298.15 K; [HSO₄]⁵¹ at 298.15 K. (b) [emim][anion] + 1-propanol: ●, [Me₂SO₄] at 293.15 K; △, [SCN] at 293.15 K; ○, [EtSO₄]⁵⁴ at 298.15 K; ■, [NTf₂]¹⁴ at 298.15 K; ×, [triflate]⁹ at 298.15 K; [HSO₄]⁵³ at 298.15 K.

Table 1. Specifications of chemical samples

Chemical name	CAS	Source	Mass fraction purity	Purification method	Water mass fraction	Water analysis method	Halides mass fraction
Ethanol	64-17-5	Sigma-Aldrich	0.999	Molecular sieve drying	$< 4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	GC ^a	-
1-Propanol	71-23-8	Sigma-Aldrich	>0.995	Molecular sieve drying	$< 4 \cdot 10^{-5}$	GC ^a	-
[emim][Me ₂ SO ₄] ^c	516474-01-4	IoLiTec	>0.99	Vacuum desiccation	$< 5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	KF ^b	$< 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$
[emim][SCN] ^d	331717-63-6	IoLiTec	>0.98	Vacuum desiccation	$< 2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	KF ^b	< 0.02

^aGC = Gas-liquid chromatography.

^bKF = Karl Fischer Titration.

^c[emim][Me₂SO₄]^c = 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium methyl sulfate

^d[emim][SCN]^d = 1-ethyl-3-methylimidazolium thiocyanate

Table 2. Coefficients of the Fitting Eqs. (10) and (11) for excess molar volume $10^6 \cdot V_m^E / \text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}$ and standard absolute deviations σ for the binary mixtures IL (1) + alcohol (2).

z	A_{0z}	A_{1z}	A_{2z}	A_{3z}	A_{4z}	$\frac{10^6 \sigma}{\text{m}^3 \cdot \text{mol}^{-1}}$
[emim][Me ₂ SO ₄] (1) + ethanol (2)						
a	$-1.163 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$-5.4051 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-3.7375 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-3.0323 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-1.2891 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.038
b	$3.3075 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.6597 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.7097 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.9685 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.5979 \cdot 10^{-2}$	
c	-4.3406	-4.4941	-4.7411	-6.2108	-1.4296	
[emim][Me ₂ SO ₄] (1) + 1-propanol (2)						
a	$-1.1163 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$-5.4051 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$-3.7375 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-3.0323 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-1.2891 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.038
b	$3.3075 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.6597 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.7097 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$2.9685 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.5989 \cdot 10^{-2}$	
c	-4.3406	-4.4941	-4.7411	-6.2108	-1.4296	
[emim][SCN] (1) + ethanol (2)						
a	$-1.9412 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.4480 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-2.4804 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$1.0962 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$3.3949 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.026
b	$8.5003 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$3.3131 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$6.0995 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-2.7864 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$-2.5625 \cdot 10^{-2}$	
c	-11.8464	0.0903	0.1727	-1.9248	4.1925	
[emim][SCN] (1) + 1-propanol (2)						
a	$-1.0319 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.6005 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-6.5402 \cdot 10^{-6}$	$6.0295 \cdot 10^{-5}$	$-4.6594 \cdot 10^{-5}$	0.030
b	$2.3545 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-4.3973 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$3.3592 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$2.5564 \cdot 10^{-3}$	$1.0675 \cdot 10^{-3}$	
c	-3.6982	0.0469	0.1353	0.8377	-2.4149	

Table 3. Coefficients of the Fitting Eqs. (10) and (11) for excess isentropic compressibilities κ_S^E/TPa and standard absolute deviations σ for the binary mixtures IL (1) + alcohol (2).

z	A_{0z}	A_{1z}	A_{2z}	A_{3z}	A_{4z}	$\frac{10^{12} \sigma}{\text{Pa}^{-1}}$
[emim][Me ₂ SO ₄] (1) + ethanol (2)						
<i>a</i>	$-3.5989 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.6825 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-2.160 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.1390 \cdot 10^{-1}$	$-4.0231 \cdot 10^{-2}$	1.036
<i>b</i>	16.874	-96.460	7.292	77.474	18.669	
<i>c</i>	-2243.0	14214.2	-571.9	-12516.8	-2352.6	
[emim][Me ₂ SO ₄] (1) + 1-propanol (2)						
<i>a</i>	$-2.0641 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.2909 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.0236 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.0328 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-8.3213 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.743
<i>b</i>	8.282	-3.594	3.115	-2.973	2.518	
<i>c</i>	-960.851	215.232	-230.493	98.402	-73.863	
[emim][SCN] (1) + ethanol (2)						
<i>a</i>	$-3.2871 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$5.3918 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-9.2580 \cdot 10^{-4}$	$2.3588 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-2.5369 \cdot 10^{-2}$	1.361
<i>b</i>	13.958	-26.827	-3.196	-3.686	4.455	
<i>c</i>	-1749.8	3664.1	771.4	-300.1	229.7	
[emim][SCN] (1) + 1-propanol (2)						
<i>a</i>	$-2.2687 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.3959 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-1.5901 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$1.1417 \cdot 10^{-2}$	$-4.6099 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.550
<i>b</i>	8.724	-3.597	5.539	-3.272	0.911	
<i>c</i>	-1001.8	184.8	-502.1	137.9	86.4	

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Table of Contents (TOC)

